

STUDIES ON 6:7-DIHYDROXY-4-METHYLCOUMARIN AND ITS METHYL ETHERS

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6:7-Dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and its dimethyl ether, on bromination with one mole of bromine, furnish the 3-bromo compound, and with two moles of bromine, the 3:8-dibromo compound. The 7-methoxy derivative, however, affords the 3:5-dibromo compound with two moles of bromine. In nitration, the 7-methoxy derivative yields the 5-nitro derivative whereas the 6:7-dimethoxy derivative furnishes the 3-nitro derivative.

Considerable work has been done on the reactivity of various mono- and dihydroxycoumarins, but the data regarding the reactivity of 6:7-dihydroxycoumarins are meagre. 6:7-Dihydroxycoumarin derivatives occur in nature and are therefore of interest. King *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 1392) and Gurbaksh Singh *et al.* (*Chem. & Ind.*, 1954, 1294) as a part of their studies on certain plant products brominated 6:7-dimethoxycoumarin and obtained the 3-bromo compound. Späth and Dobrovony (*Ber.*, 1938, 71B, 1831) nitrated 6:7-dimethoxy- and 6-methoxy-7-hydroxy-coumarins and obtained the 3-nitro compound. The present work deals with the systematic study of the pattern of substitution in the more readily accessible 6:7-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (Ia) and its 7-methoxy (Ib) and 6:7-dimethoxy (Ic) derivatives.

(I)

[(a) R=R'=H. (b) R=Me; R'=H. (c) R=R'=Me]

(Ia) on bromination with one mole of bromine afforded the 3-bromo derivative, the dimethyl ether of which furnished a coumarilic acid derivative on treatment with alkali. With two moles of bromine, the 3:8-dibromo compound was obtained, as seen by a direct comparison of its dimethyl ether with an authentic specimen, synthesised as follows:

7-Hydroxy-8-bromo-4-methylcoumarin, obtained by the Pechmann condensation of 2-bromoresorcinol with ethyl acetoacetate, on methylation and the Elbs persulphate oxidation, yielded 6-hydroxy-7-methoxy-8-bromo-4-methylcoumarin. This on bromination and methylation afforded 6:7-dimethoxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin, which on boiling with alkali furnished a bromocoumarilic acid. (Ib) afforded with one mole of bromine the 3-bromo product, but with two moles, a dibromo product was obtained, the methyl ether of which furnished a bromocoumarilic acid. As the dibromo

compound is different from the 3:8-dibromo product, described above, it must be the 3:5-dibromo derivative. (Ic) yielded the 3-bromo and the 3:8-dibromo derivatives when brominated with one and two moles of bromine respectively.

Iodination of (Ia), (Ib) and (Ic) with iodine and iodic acid, iodine and ammonia, and iodine monochloride under varying conditions did not succeed. With iodine monochloride (Ib) furnished a chloro compound which has not been investigated.

(Ia) on nitration gave rise to an unworkable mass from which no pure product could be obtained. (Ib), however, afforded a compound different from 7-methoxy-6-hydroxy-8-nitro-4-methylcoumarin, synthesised by the Elbs persulphate oxidation of 7-methoxy-8-nitro-4-methylcoumarin. It remained unchanged on heating with liquor ammonia. It is therefore 7-methoxy-6-hydroxy-5-nitro-4-methylcoumarin. On demethylation, the nitro group was eliminated and 6:7-dihydroxy-4-methylcoumarin was obtained. (Ic) on nitration yielded the 3-nitro compound which on reaction with liquor ammonia furnished 2-hydroxy-4:5-dimethoxyacetophenone. The nitro compound was reduced to the 3-amino compound and also demethylated to 6:7-dihydroxy-3-nitro-4-methylcoumarin.

The Friedel-Crafts acetylation of (Ia) and (Ib) and the Fries migration of 6:7-diacetoxy-4-methylcoumarin did not succeed, only (Ia) was obtained. 7-Methoxy-6-acetoxy-4-methylcoumarin on the Fries reaction at 120-30° furnished (Ia) and at lower temperatures, (Ib). Seshadri *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3065) have obtained 6:7-dihydroxy-8-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin by the Elbs persulphate oxidation of 7-methoxy-8-acetyl-4-methylcoumarin. It may be mentioned here that when direct substitution in 8-position is not possible, the Elbs persulphate oxidation of 7-methoxy-8-substituted coumarins offers a convenient method for the synthesis of 8-substituted 6:7-dihydroxy-coumarins.

*E X P E R I M E N T A L

Bromination.—To the coumarin derivative (2 g.), dissolved in a minimum quantity of glacial acetic acid, the required quantity of bromine solution (10% in acetic acid) was added dropwise; after 4 hours the product, which separated or was obtained by dilution with water, was washed with dilute acetic acid and then crystallised from either acetic acid or ethanol.

Methylation.—The methyl ethers were prepared by refluxing the acetone solutions of the compounds with dimethyl sulphate in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate and crystallised from acetic acid or alcohol. In the methylation of 7-methoxy-6-hydroxy-3:5-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin, benzene was used as the solvent as it was found to decompose in acetone solution.

7-Hydroxy-8-bromo-4-methylcoumarin.—To a mixture of 2-bromoresorcinol (1.9 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (1.6 c.c.), 80% H_2SO_4 (10 c.c.) was added with external cooling. The solid separating on pouring the reaction mixture next day on crushed ice was crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 255-57°, yield 1.9 g. (Found: Br, 31.3%. $C_{11}H_7O_3Br$ requires Br, 31.4%).

*All melting points are uncorrected.

The methyl ether was crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 206-208°. (Found: Br, 30.0. $C_{11}H_9O_3Br$ requires Br, 29.7%).

6-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-8-bromo-4-methylcoumarin.—The above methyl ether (2.7 g.) was dissolved in 10% NaOH (30 c.c.) by warming on a steam-bath. It was then oxidised with potassium persulphate (3 g. in 60 c.c. of distilled water) according to Parikh and Sethna (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 364). The product obtained was crystallised from dilute ethanol in needles, m.p. 220-221°. (Found: Br, 28.2. $C_{11}H_9O_4Br$ requires Br, 28.1%).

6-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-3 : 8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin.—To the above coumarin (2.8 g.), dissolved in minimum quantity of acetic acid, bromine (1.6 g.) in acetic acid (16 c.c.) was added. The product, which separated on keeping at room temperature for 2 hours, was crystallised from ethanol as yellow needles (2.8 g.), m.p. 257-58°. (Found: Br, 44.4. $C_{11}H_7O_4Br_2$ requires Br, 43.9%).

The methyl ether has been described in Table I.

TABLE I

Products obtained on bromination.

No	Substance.	Products obtained.	M.P.	Formula.	% Bromine.		Completely methylated products of the bromo compounds shown in column 3.
					Found.	Calc.	
1.	6 : 7-Dimethoxy-M	6 : 7-Dimethoxy-3-bromo-M	205-206°	$C_{13}H_{11}O_4Br$	26.4	26.7	...
2.	"	6 : 7-Dimethoxy-3 : 8-dibromo-M	215-16°	$C_{12}H_{10}O_4Br_2$	42.8	42.3	...
3.	7-Methoxy-6-hydroxy-M	7-Methoxy-6-hydroxy-3-bromo-M	237-38°	$C_{11}H_9O_4Br$	28.6	28.1	a
4.	"	7-Methoxy-6-hydroxy-3 : 5-dibromo-M *	200°	$C_{11}H_9O_4Br_2$	44.3	44.0	b
5.	6 : 7-Dihydroxy-M	6 : 7-Dihydroxy-3-bromo-M	244-45°	$C_{10}H_7O_4Br$	30.1	29.5	c
6.	"	6 : 7-Dihydroxy-3 : 8-dibromo-M	267-68°	$C_{10}H_6O_4Br_2$	45.1	45.7	d

a. Methyl ether same as 1 (column 3).

b. Methyl ether, m.p. 195°. (Found: Br, 43.00. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4Br_2$ requires Br, 42.3%).

c. Methyl ether same as 1 (column 3).

d. Methyl ether same as 2 (column 3).

*. Obtained on heating the parent compound with 4 mols. of bromine in acetic acid on a steam-bath for 4 hours. Product crystallised from alcohol in needles.

M denotes -4-methylcoumarin (columns 2 and 3).

5 : 6-Dimethoxy-3-methylcoumarilic Acid.—6 : 7-Dimethoxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin (0.5 g.) was refluxed with alcoholic potash (25 c.c., 10%) for 2 hours on a steam-bath. The product, obtained on acidification of the diluted solution, was purified through sodium bicarbonate solution. It was crystallised from acetic acid in thin plates, m.p. 220°. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 5.3. $C_{12}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 61.0; H, 5.1%). It developed a violet coloration with H_2SO_4 (conc).

5:6-Dimethoxy-7-bromo-3-methylcoumarilic acid was obtained from 6:7-dimethoxy-3:8-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin as above. It was crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 270-72°. (Found: Br, 25.5. $C_{12}H_{11}O_5Br$ requires Br, 25.4%). It developed a violet coloration with H_2SO_4 (warm, conc.).

5:6-Dimethoxy-4-bromo-3-methylcoumarilic acid was obtained from 6:7-dimethoxy-3:5-dibromo-4-methylcoumarin as above and crystallised from acetic acid in white needles, m.p. 240-44° (decomp.). (Found: Br, 25.2. $C_{12}H_{11}O_5Br$ requires Br, 25.4%). It showed a greenish coloration with H_2SO_4 (warm, conc.).

6-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-8-nitro-4-methylcoumarin.—7-Methoxy-8-nitro-4-methylcoumarin (1 g.) was oxidised with potassium persulphate as usual. The product obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 255-56° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.6. $C_{11}H_9O_6N$ requires N, 5.6%).

6:7-Dimethoxy-3-nitro-4-methylcoumarin.—6:7-Dimethoxy-4-methylcoumarin (2.2 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid and a mixture of nitric acid (2 c.c.) and acetic acid (6 c.c.) was added dropwise at room temperature with stirring. Bright yellow needles separated after stirring for some time. The reaction mixture was poured on crushed ice and filtered. The product obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in bright yellow needles, m.p. 215-17°. (Found: N, 4.9. $C_{12}H_{11}O_6N$ requires N, 5.2%).

The above 3-nitrocoumarin (1 g.) was boiled with liquor ammonia (60 c.c.) for 2½ hours on a steam-bath; the solution obtained on acidification was extracted with ether and the residue obtained after removal of ether was extracted with benzene. The product obtained on removal of benzene was crystallised from water, m.p. 112-14°. Mixed m.p. with 2-hydroxy-4:5-dimethoxyacetophenone, prepared according to Bargellini and Aureli (*Atti R. Accad. Lincei*, 1911, v, 20, 118) was not depressed.

6:7-Dimethoxy-3-amino-4-methylcoumarin.—To 6:7-dimethoxy-3-nitro-4-methylcoumarin (2.6 g.) and stannous chloride (14 g.), HCl (conc., 100 c.c.) was added and the reaction mixture heated under reflux for 3 hours. It was made alkaline with ammonia and repeatedly extracted with ether. The pale yellow solid obtained on removal of ether was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in silky needles (1.3 g.), m.p. 164-65°. (Found: N, 5.6. $C_{12}H_{13}O_4N$ requires N, 6.0%).

6:7-Dihydroxy-3-nitro-4-methylcoumarin.—6:7-Dimethoxy-3-nitro-4-methylcoumarin was demethylated with hydriodic acid in acetic anhydride. The product obtained was crystallised from very dilute alcohol in thin plates, m.p. 229-30°. (Found: N, 6.0. $C_{10}H_7O_6N$ requires N, 5.9%).

6-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-5-nitro-4-methylcoumarin.—7-Methoxy-6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (2.06 g.) was suspended in acetic acid (40 c.c.) and a mixture of fuming nitric acid (2 c.c.) and acetic acid (6 c.c.) was added dropwise at room temperature with stirring. The product separating was crystallised from alcohol in thin plates, m.p. 220-22° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.2. $C_{11}H_9O_6N$ requires N, 5.6%).

One of the authors (M. G. P.) thanks the Government of India for the award of a research scholarship.